

**EXPLORING DIFFERENT FORMULATIONS OF *KANTAKARI*
(*SOLANUM VIRGINIANUM* LINN): INSIGHTS FROM
BRIHADATRAYI**

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ABSTRACT

Kantakari (*Solanum virginianum* Linn), a perennial diffused herb belonging to the family Solanaceae, is widely recognized in Ayurveda for its broad-spectrum medicinal applications. Various plant parts, including root, leaves, floral bud, flower, fruit, seed and whole plant are employed in numerous traditional formulations such as *Svarasa* (fresh juice), *Kalka* (paste), *Kvatha* (decoction), *Churna* (powder), *Taila* (medicated oil), *Ghrita* (medicated ghee), *Basti* (enema) and many others are used for both internal and external therapeutic purposes. Pharmacological studies attribute its bronchodilator, antiasthmatic, antitussive, antimicrobial, insecticidal, immunomodulatory and other therapeutic activities. The present review compiles 320 formulations containing *Kantakari* from Brihadatrayi, underscoring its longstanding significance in classical Ayurvedic pharmacopeia. Analysis of these

formulations reveals that documentation of medicated ghee (74), followed by enema (62) and decoction (36) formulations in the maximum numbers indicating their significant role in traditional therapeutic practice.

KEYWORDS: *Kantakari*, formulations, pharmacological studies.

INTRODUCTION

Kantakari (*Solanum virginianum* Linn) is a member of the Solanaceae family and is a diffuse herb characterized by numerous prickles on its stems and leaves. It is well documented in all Samhita and Nighantu Grantha for its therapeutic efficacy in various diseases. The plant exhibits properties such as *Dipana* (appetizer), *Pachana* (digestive), and *Vata Kaphahara* (alleviates *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha*). It is traditionally indicated in conditions like *Svasa* (respiratory disorders or asthma), *Kasa* (cough), *Pinasa* (rhinitis), *Jvara* (fever), *Parsvapida* (flank pain), *Krimi* (worm infestations) and *Hridayaroga* (cardiac disorders). Various parts of it including root, leaves, floral bud, flower, fruit, seed and whole plant are used in Ayurvedic formulations such as *Svarasa* (fresh juice), *Kalka* (paste), *Kvatha* (decoction), *Churna* (powder), *Ghrita* (medicated ghee), *Taila* (medicated oil), and many other preparations.

Ayurvedic formulations include both internal and external applications, utilizing a wide range of dosage forms administered through various methods. Internal administration includes *Avaleha* (medicated linctus), *Lavana* (salt based formulations), *Pathya Kalpana* (food preparations) and many others. External applications include *Svedana* (sudation), *Abhyanga* (massage), *Lepa* (external application), *Aschotana* (eye drops), *Nasya* (nasal instillation), *Anjana* (collyrium), *Kavala* (gargling), *Gandusha* (mouthwash), *Dhumapana* (medicated smoking), *Basti* (enema) and others. Formulations administered internally and externally include powder, medicated ghee, medicated oils, decoctions, medicated milk preparations and many others.

The plant exhibits various pharmacological activities such as ethanol and aqueous extract of the fruit, root and whole plant have been reported to possess immunomodulatory properties.¹ Leaf extracts demonstrate significant antibacterial² and bronchodilating³ effects, whereas aqueous extracts of the flowers exhibit notable anti-asthmatic activity.⁴ These findings highlight the therapeutic potential of the plant and provide a basis for its incorporation into various traditional and modern formulations. The present review aims to analyze the usage patterns of *Kantakari* containing formulations from Ayurvedic compendiums such as Brihadatrayi, focusing on its various therapeutic potentials and traditional applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

References regarding to formulations containing *Kantakari* were compiled from Brihadatrayi (Table no: 1). Additionally, relevant information was retrieved from electronic sources such as Google Scholar, PubMed, AYUSH Research Portal and DHARA, along with various

research papers on the plant.

Table No. 1: List of classical texts mentioned *Kantakari* formulations with their abbreviations.

No.	Name of classical texts	Abbreviations
1.	Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana/ Sharirasthana/ Chikitsasthana/ Siddhisthana/ Kalpasthana ^[5]	Cha.Su./ Cha.Sha./ Cha.Chi./ Cha.Si./ Cha.K
2.	Sushruta Samhita Sutrasthana/ Chikitsasthana/ Kalpasthana/ Uttaratantra ^[6]	Su.Su./ Su.Chi./ Su.Ka./ Su.Ut
6.	Ashtanga Hridaya Chikitsasthana/ Uttarasthana ^[7]	A.H.Chi./ A.H.Ut.

RESULTS

Different formulations of *Kantakari*

A comprehensive review of three classical Ayurvedic compendia was conducted to identify formulations containing *Kantakari*. The screening revealed a total of 320 formulations, classified into 24 distinct dosage forms intended for both internal and external therapeutic use. These include fresh juice (3), paste (2), decoction (36), powder (11), *Gutika/Vataka* (pills/tablet, 1), *Kshirapaka* (medicated milk, 23), *Avaleha* (medicated linctus, 18), *Sandhana* preparations (medicated fermentations, 8), medicated oil (27), medicated ghee (74), other *Sneha* preparations (other oleaginous preparations, 6), *Kshara/Lavana* (alkali/ salt preparations, 3), enema (62), collyrium (3), *Dhumavarti* (medicated smoking stick, 1), and *Pradhamana Nasya* (Errhine insufflation, 1). In addition, *Kantakari* is incorporated into *Pathya Kalpana* (food preparations), including *Yusha* (medicated lentil soup, 7), *Yavagu* (medicated gruel, 5), *Peya* (thin gruel, 9), *Mamsarasa* (meat soup, 3), *Siddha Jala* (medicated water, 8), *Saktu* (roasted flour preparation, 1) and *Bhojya* (food preparations, 1).

Every Ayurvedic dosage form is intended to address specific therapeutic needs, incorporating *Kantakari* and its formulations to manage a wide spectrum of health conditions as described in classical Ayurvedic texts. These formulations are developed for both internal and external applications and are administered through various therapeutic routes. For instance, decoction is employed for internal use as *Pana* (oral administration) and in externally utilized in sudation, *Parisechana* (Irrigation), *Prakshalana* (washing), mouthwash. Medicated milk is administered as orally and utilized for *Karnapurana* (ear instillation), sudation, and irrigation. Medicated oils are indicated for oral administration, nasal instillation, massage, mouthwash. Similarly, medicated *Ghee* are used for both oral administration and nasal instillation.

Fresh juice

Freshly extracted juice mixed with honey, prepared from the whole plant, is used internally in the management of *Kasa* (cough) and *Mutradosha* (urinary disorders). Ethnomedically, the expressed juice of the leaves is administered with black pepper in rheumatism, while the fruit juice is employed for the management of sore throat.^[8,9]

Table No. 2: *Kantakari* used in fresh juice form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Sharkaradiyoga Svarasa</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.18/106
2.	<i>Nidigdhika Svarasa</i>	<i>Mutradosha</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.58/39
3.	<i>Kantakari Svarasa</i>	<i>Mutraghata</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.11/12

Paste

Root is used in paste forms. Paste of root is used for *Pumsavana Karma* (ritual for male child). Ethnomedically, paste prepared from fresh fruits is applied in pimples and swellings. Paste of fresh leaves or its powder mixed with water is applied in the management of piles.^[10] Root paste is used in the treatment of Hernia.^[11]

Table No. 3: *Kantakari* used in paste form

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Svetabruhatimula Kalka</i>	<i>Pumsavanakarma</i>	Root	A.H.Sha. 1/40
2.	<i>Gandharvahastadi Kalka</i>	<i>Ashmari</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.11/21

Decoction

Whole plant and root are used in decoction formulations. They are administered in conditions such as fever, *Svasa* (dyspnoea/asthma), cough, *Hikka* (hiccup), *Shula* (pain), *Gulma* (abdominal lump/tumor), *Aruchi* (anorexia) and others. Externally, they are intended for sudation, sprinkling, washing, gargling and holding in mouth. Ethnomedically, a decoction of the root is administered with the addition of long pepper and honey in cough and catarrh and with rock salt and asafoetida in spasmodic cough. A decoction of the whole plant is employed in gonorrhoea, while washing with a decoction of the leaves is used in fever among children.^[12] Research indicates that a decoction of the root exhibits considerable anti-inflammatory activity against prostaglandin and arachidonic acid metabolites.^[13]

Table No. 4: *Kantakari* used in decoction form

No.	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
Internal administration				
1.	<i>Haritakyadi Kvatha</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.1/1/76
2.	<i>Bruhatyadi Kvatha</i>	<i>Sannipata Jvara</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.3/210
3.	<i>Bruhatyadi Gana Kvatha</i>	<i>Sannipata Jvara</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.3/213
4.	<i>Dashamula Kvatha</i>	<i>Trishna in Svasa, Kasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.17/105
5.	<i>Dashamula Kvatha</i>	<i>Vedanavanta Vrana</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.25/77
6.	<i>Panchamula Kvatha</i>	<i>Pitavruta Vata</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.28/186
7.	<i>Dashamuli Kvatha</i>	<i>Virechana</i>	Root	Su.Su.44/61
8.	<i>Mahatpanchamulyadi Kvatha</i>	<i>Virechana</i>	Root	Su.Su.44/80
9.	<i>Brihatpanchamulyadi Kvatha</i>	<i>Vataja Visarpa</i>	Root	Su.Chi.17/5
10.	<i>Ashmarinashaka Kvatha</i>	<i>Vataja Ashmari</i>	Whole plant	Su.Chi.7/5
11.	<i>Bilva Kvatha</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Root	Su.Chi.28/11
12.	<i>Haridradi Kvatha</i>	<i>Jvara, Kasa, Aruchi</i>	Root	Su.Ut.39/205
13.	<i>Dashamuli Kvatha</i>	<i>Vishama Jvara</i>	Root	Su.Ut.39/216
14.	<i>Eranda Dvadasha Kvatha</i>	<i>Gulma, Shula</i>	Root	Su.Ut.42/112
15.	<i>Nagaradi Kvatha</i>	<i>Kukshishula</i>	Seed	Su.Ut.42/128
16.	<i>Dashamuladi Kvatha</i>	<i>Vataja Hridroga</i>	Root	Su.Ut.43/11
17.	<i>Panchagana Kvatha</i>	<i>Vataja Trishna</i>	Root	Su.Ut.48/20
18.	<i>Yavadi Kvatha</i>	<i>Udavarta</i>	Fruit	Su.Ut.55/51
19.	<i>Kantakari Kvatha</i>	<i>Basti- Parshva- Shula</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.1/28
20.	<i>Pippalyadi Kvatha</i>	<i>Jvara</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.1/52
21.	<i>Vyaghrayadi Kvatha</i>	<i>Jvara, Svasa, Kasa</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.1/61
22.	<i>Vyaghrayadi Kvatha</i>	<i>Sannipataja Jvara</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.1/65
23.	<i>Triphaladi Kvatha</i>	<i>Jvara, Kasa</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.1/91
24.	<i>Dashamuladi Kvatha</i>	<i>Hikka, Svasa</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.4/24
25.	<i>Dashamula Kvatha</i>	<i>Hikka, Svasa, Pipasa</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.4/28
26.	<i>Dashamula Kvatha</i>	<i>Vatatmaka Stanya</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.2/9
27.	<i>Dashamula Kvatha</i>	<i>Vataroga</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.28/41
External application				
28.	<i>Shyonakadi Kvatha Pralepa</i>	<i>Urustambha</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.27/56
29.	<i>Dashmula Kvatha Sveda</i>	<i>Vataroga</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.28/111
30.	<i>Dvipanchamula Kvatha Parisheka</i>	<i>Vrana</i>	Root	Su.Chi.1/77
31.	<i>Dashamula Kvatha Nadi Sveda</i>	<i>Ruja</i>	Root	A.H.Su.17/9
32.	<i>Panchamula Kvatha Prakshalana</i>	<i>Vidradhi</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.13/2
33.	<i>Vrushchikaliadi Kvatha Parisheka</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.15/49
34.	<i>Dashamula Kvatha Gandusha</i>	<i>Dantachala</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.22/14
35.	<i>Vyaghri Kvatha Gandusha</i>	<i>Dantashula</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Ut.22/22
36.	<i>Kshudradi Kvatha Kavala</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Ut.22/97

Powder

The powder of the whole plant mixed with honey is administered in cough. Research has also shown that it has significant efficacy in chronic bronchitis among children^[14] and in bronchial

asthma.^[15] Whole plant and root are utilized in powder formulations, and they are therapeutically indicated in conditions including dyspnoea/asthma, cough, *Kshata* (chest injury), *Kshaya* (phthisis/emaciation), abdominal lump/tumor, *Prameha* (urinary disorders/diabetes), *Anaha* (constipation/flatulence), *Shotha* (edema/inflammation), *Kushtha* (skin diseases), *Shula* (pain), *Pandu* (anemia), *Mutraghata* (urinary diseases), urinary stone and others. They are also recommended during the eighth month of antenatal care in pregnancy.

Table No. 5: Kantakari used in powder form

No.	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Pippalyadi Churna</i>	<i>Shotha</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.12/41
2.	<i>Mustadi Churna</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.7/66
3.	<i>Arishtadi Churna</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	Root	Su.Chi.9/46
4.	<i>Pathadi Churna</i>	<i>Prameha, Pidaka</i>	Whole plant	Su.Chi.12/9
5.	<i>Vrikshadanadi Churna</i>	<i>Aamatisara</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.40/41
6.	<i>Nidigdihikadi Churna</i>	<i>Svasa</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.51/55
7.	<i>Rajanyadi Churna</i>	<i>Vatanulomana, Atisara, Jvara, Svasa, Kamala, Pandu</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Ut.2/38
8.	<i>Bruhatyadi Garbharakshaka Yoga</i>	<i>Ashtamamsa Garbhini Paricharya</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Sha.2/58
9.	<i>Vyaghri Churna Leha</i>	<i>Kaphaja Kasa</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.3/48
10.	<i>Yavanyadi Churna</i>	<i>Raktaja Arsha</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.8/116
11.	<i>Pippalyadi Churna</i>	<i>Mandagni</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.10/12

Pills / Tablets

Whole plant is used in Brihani Gutika formulation. It is indicated in *Vajikarana* (aphrodisiac therapy).

Table No. 6: Kantakari used in Pills / Tablet form

No.	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Bruhani Gutika</i>	<i>Vajikarana</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.2/1/24

Medicated milk

Root and whole plant are used in medicated milk preparations. Internally, they are administered in conditions such as fever, (*Yakshma*) tuberculosis/consumptive disorders, *Yonivyapada* (gynecological disorders), *Vatarakta* (gout/arthritis) and urinary stone. They are also employed in aphrodisiac therapy and *Virechana Yoga* (purgation therapy) and are indicated for use in the eighth month of antenatal care regimen. Externally, they are used for sprinkling, pouring of, sudation and ear instillation. Medicated milk prepared with its roots and whole plant is also used for instillation in the ear in *Karnashula* (earache) and for pouring

into the eyes in *Abhishyanda* (conjunctivitis/ophthalmic inflammation) respectively.

Table No. 7: *Kantakari* used in medicated milk form

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
Internal application				
1.	<i>Apatyakara Kshirayoga</i>	<i>Vajikarana</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.2/3/8
2.	<i>Panchamula Kshirapaka</i>	<i>Jirna Jvara</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.3/234
3.	<i>Trikantaka Siddha Kshira</i>	<i>Jvara</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.3/236
4.	<i>Panchamula Siddha Kshira</i>	<i>Kasa, Svarabheda in Yakshma</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.8/96
5.	<i>Baladi Kshirapaka</i>	<i>Yakshma</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.8/114
6.	<i>Dashamulashrita Kshira</i>	<i>Shula</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.29/124
7.	<i>Laghupanchamuladi Kshira</i>	For <i>Virechana</i>	Root	Cha.K.11/9
8.	<i>Mahasahadi Kshira</i>	<i>Garbhini Vedana</i>	Whole plant	Su.Sha.10/61
9.	<i>Kapitthadi Kshirapaka</i>	<i>Ashtamasha Garbhini Paricharya</i>	Root	Su.Sha.10/67, A.H.Sha.2/58
10.	<i>Panchamuli Shrita Kshira</i>	<i>Ashmari</i>	Root	Su.Ut.55/26
11.	<i>Shunthyadi Kshira</i>	<i>Jvara, Svasa</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.1/114
12.	<i>Dashamuladi Kshira</i>	<i>Rajyakshama</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.5/95
13.	<i>Balabilva Shrita Paya</i>	<i>Jvara</i>	Fruit	A.H.Chi.1/112
14.	<i>Vruschiradi Paya</i>	<i>Jvara Shopha</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.1/115
15.	<i>Baladi Shrita Paya</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.22/8
16.	<i>Laghupanchamula Shrita Kshira</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.22/57
External application				
17.	<i>Dashamula Shrita Kshira Parisechana</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.29/125
18.	<i>Kantakari Kshira Parisechana</i>	<i>Vataja Abhishyanda</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.9/12
19.	<i>Kantakarimula Kshirapaka Karnapurana</i>	<i>Karnashula</i>	Root	Su.Ut.9/14
20.	<i>Dashamula Kshira Parisheka</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.22/23
21.	<i>Dashamula Kshira Parisheka</i>	<i>Vataja Shiroroga</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.24/3
22.	<i>Panchamula Paya Parisheka</i>	<i>Sandhimukta</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.27/19

Medicated linctus

Root and whole plant are used in medicated linctus formulations. They are indicated in conditions such as dyspnea/asthma, cough, *Kshata* (chest injury/hemoptysis), phthisis, *Shotha* (inflammation/edema), tuberculosis, *Arsha* (piles/hemorrhoids), abdominal lump, *Antravidhi* (intestinal obstruction), *Kushtha* (skin diseases), cardiac disorders, urinary disorders/diabetes, and anemia. They are also used as purgation therapy and for *Rasayana Karma* (rejuvenative therapy). Research also indicates that *Kantakari Avaleha* exhibits antitussive activity^[16] and anti-inflammatory activity.^[17] Research has further shown its significant effect in bronchial asthma.^[18]

Table No. 8: Kantakari used in Medicated linctus form.

No.	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Bramha Rasayana</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.1/1/41
2.	<i>Chyavanaprasha</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.1/1/62
3.	<i>Indrokta Rasayana</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.1/4/69
4.	<i>Ghrita Guda</i>	<i>Kshatakshina, Svasa, Kasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi. 11/56
5.	<i>Kamsaharitaki</i>	<i>Shvayathu</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.12/50
6.	<i>Chitrakadi Leha</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi. 18/54
7.	<i>Agastya Haritaki</i>	<i>Rasayana, Kasa, Svasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi. 18/57
8.	<i>Danti- Dravanti Avaleha</i>	<i>Virechana</i>	Root	Cha.K.12/15
9.	<i>Agastya Avaleha</i>	<i>Rajyakshma, Grahani</i>	Root	Su.Ut.52/43
10.	<i>Kantakari Avaleha</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa, Gulma, Arsha</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.3/63
11.	<i>Agastya Haritaki Rasayana</i>	<i>Kasa, Rasayana, Kshaya</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.3/127
12.	<i>Vasishtha Rasayana</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Fruit, root	A.H.Chi.3/134
13.	<i>Dashamuladi Leha</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	Root	A.H.Chi. 5/21
14.	<i>Dashamula Guda</i>	<i>Arsha, Gulma</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.8/151
15.	<i>Sukumara Rasayana</i>	<i>Antravruddhi</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.13/41
16.	<i>Dashamula Haritaki</i>	<i>Shvayathu</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.17/14
17.	<i>Bramha Rasayana</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Root	A.H.Ut. 39/15
18.	<i>Chyavanaprasha</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Root	A.H.Ut. 39/33

Fermented formulations

Root and whole plant are used in fermented formulations. Internally, they are administered in conditions such as piles, *Grahani* (malabsorption syndrome/irritable bowel disorder), fistula-in-ano, inflammation/edema, hiccup, *Kilasa* (leucoderma/vitiligo), skin diseases, *Vata-Kaphaja Roga* (disorders caused by vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha*), urinary disorders/diabetes, *Krimi* (helminthiasis/worm infestation), *Arbuda* (tumor/neoplasm), anemia, *Raktapitta* (bleeding disorders/hemorrhagic conditions), *Aruchi* (anorexia/loss of appetite), itching, and others.

Table No. 9: Kantakari used in fermented formulations form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Triphalasava</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.6/81
2.	<i>Gandirarishta</i>	<i>Shotha, Arsha, Bhagandara, Krimi</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.12/29
3.	<i>Punarnavadyarishta</i>	<i>Shotha, Hikka, Kilasa, Kandu</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.12/34
4.	<i>Dantyarishta</i>	<i>Arsha, Grahani</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.14/144
5.	<i>Mulasava</i>	<i>Grahani, Raktapitta, Hridaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.15/156
6.	<i>Dvipanchamuladi Arishta</i>	<i>Arsha, Grahani, Pandu</i>	Root	Su.Chi.6/14
7.	<i>Vrushchikadi Arishta</i>	<i>Gulma, Aruchi</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.42/46
8.	<i>Dantyarishta</i>	<i>Arsha, Anulomana</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.8/68

Medicated oil

Root, whole plant and fruit are used in medicated oil formulations. They are administered in disorders such as malabsorption syndrome, *Visarpa* (erysipelas/herpes zoster), *Vatarakta* (gout), *Yoni Vyapada* (gynecological disorders), *Kaphaja Roga* (diseases caused by *Kapha Dosh*), *Sutika Roga* (puerperal disorders), fever, urinary disorders/diabetes, *Balagraha* (pediatric afflictions due to *Graha*), *Unmada* (insanity/psychosis), *Apasmara* (epilepsy), ear disorders, and others. Externally, they are used in neuromuscular disorders, *Vrana* (wounds/ulcers) and in postnatal care in the form of nasal instillation and oil massage. Certain formulations are indicated for both internal and external use, particularly in the management of neuromuscular disorders.

Table No. 10: *Kantakari* used in medicated oil form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Panchamuladhya Taila</i>	<i>Grahani</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.15/92
2.	<i>Dashamula Taila</i>	<i>Granthi Visarpa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.21/122
3.	<i>Amrutadi Taila</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.29/104
4.	<i>Guduchyadi Taila</i>	<i>Vataja Yonivyapada</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.30/60
5.	<i>Dashamula Taila</i>	<i>Kaphaja Roga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.4/17
6.	<i>Shatavaryadi Taila</i>	<i>Basti Marmaghata</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Si.9/8
7.	<i>Samshodhana Taila</i>	<i>Vrana Shodhana</i>	Whole plant	Su.Su.37/18
8.	<i>Dvipanchamulasiddha Taila</i>	<i>Avaranakrita Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	Su.Chi.5/7
9.	<i>Dvipanchamulasiddha Taila</i>	<i>Vataja Kushtha</i>	Root	Su.Chi.9/7
10.	<i>Bala Taila</i>	<i>Sutika, Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	Su.Chi.15/29
11.	<i>Saunfyadi Taila</i>	<i>Vataja Visarpa</i>	Root	Su.Chi.17/5
12.	<i>Dvipanchamuladi Taila</i>	<i>Prameha, Udara</i>	Root	Su.Ut.41/48
13.	<i>Svadamstradi Taila</i>	<i>Vataja Mutrakrichchha</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.59/1
14.	<i>Bala Taila</i>	<i>Sutika, Vata Vikara</i>	Root	A.H.Sha.2/47
15.	<i>Pippalyadi Taila</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.8/89
16.	<i>Dashamuladi Taila</i>	<i>Arti</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.9/42
17.	<i>Dashamuladi Taila</i>	<i>Mutraghata</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.11/2
18.	<i>Sahacharadi Taila</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.21/67
19.	<i>Jivanti Taila</i>	<i>Urdhva Jatrugatavikara, Vataleshmaja Vikara</i>	Fruit	A.H.Ut.13/54
20.	<i>Erandadi Taila</i>	<i>Urdhvajatrugata Roga</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.13/55
21.	<i>Hriberadi Taila</i>	<i>Timira</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.13/70
External application				
22.	<i>Anu Taila Nasya</i>	<i>Indriya Daurbalya</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Su.5/64
23.	<i>Agurvadi Taila Nasya</i>	<i>Shita Jvara</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.3/267
24.	<i>Anu Taila Nasya</i>	<i>Pratishyaya</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.26/140
25.	<i>Saireyakadi Taila Abhyanga</i>	<i>Khalitya, Palitya</i>	Whole plant	Su.Chi.20/22
26.	<i>Anu Taila Nasya</i>	<i>Urdhvajatrugata Roga</i>	Root	A.H.Su.20/37
27.	<i>Shigruvadadi Taila Nasya</i>	<i>Apinasa, Putinasa</i>	Seed	A.H.Ut.20/22

Medicated Ghee

Whole plant and root are used in medicated *Ghee* formulations. They are administered in conditions such as fever, abdominal lump, chest injury/trauma, debility/emaciation, phthisis/tuberculosis, psychosomatic disorders, neurological/neuromuscular disorders, epilepsy, insanity/psychosis, cough, dyspnea/asthma, cardiac disorders, and pain, among others. Externally, they are used in *Urdhvajatrugata Vikara* (diseases of the head and neck region) in the form of nasal instillation. Research has shown that *Kantakari Ghrita* is efficacious in the management of bronchial asthma^[19] and dry cough.^[20]

Table No. 11: *Kantakari* used in Medicated *Ghee* formulations

No.	Formulation	Indication	Part Used	Reference
1.	<i>Pippalyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Jirna Jvara</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.3/219
2.	<i>Baladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Jvara</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.3/224
3.	<i>Trayushanadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.5/66
4.	<i>Nilinyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.5/106
5.	<i>Dashamuli Ghrita</i>	<i>Kaphaja Gulma</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.5/142
6.	<i>Dashamula Ghrita</i>	<i>Svarabodhana</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.8/97
7.	<i>Panchapanchamula Ghrita</i>	<i>Shula, Kasa, Svasa, Jvara in Yakshma</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.8/99
8.	<i>Jivantyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Yakshma</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.8/111
9.	<i>Dashamuladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Shira-Parshva-Amsha Shula, Kasa, Svasa in Yakshma</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.8/168
10.	<i>Lashunadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Unmada, Vatakaphaja Roga</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.9/52
11.	<i>Mahapanchagavya Ghrita</i>	<i>Apsmara, Unmada</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.10/18
12.	<i>Amrutaprasha Ghrita</i>	<i>Kshata, Kshina</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.11/35
13.	<i>Panchakola Ghrita</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.13/113
14.	<i>Sunishnaka Changeri Ghrita</i>	<i>Arsha, Raktastrava</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.14/237
15.	<i>Dashamuladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Grahani</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.15/82
16.	<i>Kshara Ghrita</i>	<i>Kaphaja Grahani</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.15/171
17.	<i>Kantakari Ghrita</i>	<i>Vataja Kasa</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.18/35
18.	<i>Pippalyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Svasa, Kasa, Hikka, Hridaparshva Shula</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.18/37
19.	<i>Rasna Ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.18/43
20.	<i>Dashamuladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.18/123
21.	<i>Kantakari Ghrita</i>	<i>Sarva Kasa</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.18/125
22.	<i>Dvipanchamuli Ghrita</i>	<i>Kshayaja Kasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.18/158
23.	<i>Guduchyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Kshayaja Kasa</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.18/161
24.	<i>Dashamula Taila</i>	<i>Visarpa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.21/122
25.	<i>Sthiradi Ghrita</i>	<i>Mutrakrichchha</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.26/74
26.	<i>Sthiradi Ghrita</i>	<i>Pitaja Hridaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.26/95
27.	<i>Drakshadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Pitaja Hridaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.26/96
28.	<i>Mayura Ghrita</i>	<i>Shiroroga, Ardita,</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.26/163

		<i>Urdhvajatrugata Roga</i>		
29.	<i>Mahamayura Ghrita</i>	<i>Shiroroga, Svasa, Kasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.26/166
30.	<i>Jivaniya Ghrita</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.29/61
31.	<i>Dashamula Ghrita</i>	<i>Virechana</i>	Root	Cha.K.12/9
32.	<i>Dvipanchamulasiddha Ghrita</i>	<i>Annada Shishu Arogya</i>	Root	Su.Sha.10/50
33.	<i>Neela Ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	Whole plant	Su.Chi.9/32
34.	<i>Mahaneela Ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha, Svitra</i>	Whole plant	Su.Chi.9/35
35.	<i>Saunfyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Vataja Visarpa</i>	Root	Su.Chi.17/5
36.	<i>Panchamuladvaya Ghrita</i>	<i>Naigamesha Pratishedha</i>	Root	Su.Ut.36/5
37.	<i>Suvahadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Svasa</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.51/24
38.	<i>Pathadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa, Svarabheda</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.52/31
39.	<i>Kulathadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Vatika Apasmara</i>	Root	Su.Ut.61/28
40.	<i>Panchagavya Ghrita</i>	<i>Apasmara, Unmada, Kshaya</i>	Root	Su.Ut.61/34
41.	<i>Pippalyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Jvara, Vishamagni, Kshaya</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.1/90
42.	<i>Guduchikantakari Ghrita</i>	<i>Vataja Kasa</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.3/3
43.	<i>Kantakari Ghrita</i>	<i>Svasa, Hikka, Kaphajaroga</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.3/63
44.	<i>Amrutaprasha Ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa, Nashtashukra, Chhardi, Murchha</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.3/95
45.	<i>Rasnadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Vataroga, Kasa</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.3/6
46.	<i>Dashamula Ghrita</i>	<i>Vatakaphaja Roga</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.3/56
47.	<i>Chavyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa, Kshaya</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.3/159
48.	<i>Vrishadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa, Jvara, Aruchi</i>	Leaves, root, floral bud	A.H.Chi.3/164
49.	<i>Kanadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Svasa, Hikka</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.4/51
50.	<i>Dashamula Ghrita</i>	<i>Rajyakshama</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.5/14
51.	<i>Jivantyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Rajyakshama</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.5/16
52.	<i>Panchapanchamula Ghrita</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.5/21
53.	<i>Panchamuladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Grahani, Dipana, Shula</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.10/27
54.	<i>Kshara Ghrita</i>	<i>Mandagni</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.10/64
55.	<i>Varunadi Gana Ghrita</i>	<i>Kaphaja Ashamari</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.11/25
56.	<i>Pashanabhedadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Vatashmari</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.11/18
57.	<i>Dhanvantara Ghrita</i>	<i>Prameha, Meha Pitika</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.12/19
58.	<i>Dadhika Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.14/13
59.	<i>Neelini Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma, Kushtha, Udararoga, Vyanga, Shotha, Shvitra</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.14/55
60.	<i>Dashamuladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Kaphaja Gulma</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.14/79
61.	<i>Dashamuladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.15/5
62.	<i>Yavadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.15/8
63.	<i>Vajraka Ghrita</i>	<i>Visarpa, Jvara, Kamala, Kushtha</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.19/18
64.	<i>Maha Vajraka Ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha, Svitra, Vriddhi, Gulma</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.19/20
65.	<i>Nimbadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Vata Roga, Nadivrana, Kasa,</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.21/58

		<i>Bhagandara, Gulma, Shopha</i>		
66.	<i>Vachadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Dantotapatti</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Ut.2/37
67.	<i>Anantadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Balagraha</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.3/50
68.	<i>Rasnadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Sarvarogahara, Graha</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.3/51
69.	<i>Mahabhutarava Ghrita</i>	<i>Sarvagraha</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.5/20
70.	<i>Mahapanchagavya Ghrita</i>	<i>Apasmara</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.7/19
71.	<i>Mahatriphala Ghrita</i>	<i>Netravikara</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Ut.13/12
72.	<i>Dashamula Ghrita</i>	<i>Vataja Timira</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.13/49
73.	<i>Bruhatyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Dantashula</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Ut.30/2
External application				
74.	<i>Mayuradi Ghrita Nasya</i>	<i>Urdhavajatruroga</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.24/47

Other Sneha Dravya (oleaginous formulations)

Root and Whole plant are used in *Vasa* (muscular fat), *Majja* (bone marrow) and *Mahasneha* (all oleaginous formulations) formulations. They are administered in conditions such as *Vatavyadhi* (neuromuscular disorders), *Kshina Majja* (bone marrow depletion), *Shukraroga* (disorders of semen), gout, tumor/cyst, and cardiac disorders.

Table No. 12: *Kantakari* used in other oleaginous formulations form.

No.	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Dashamuladi Siddha Majja</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi, Kshinamajja, Kshinashukra</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.28/125
2.	<i>Dashamuladi Siddha Vasa</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.28/128
3.	<i>Triphaladi Mahasneha</i>	<i>Shira- Majja- Asthigata Vata</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.28/130
4.	<i>Jivakadi Mahasneha</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.29/72
5.	<i>Dashamulasiddha Mahasneha</i>	<i>Aamaja Granthi</i>	Root	Su.Chi.18/4
6.	<i>Rasnadi Mahasneha</i>	<i>Vataroga, Hridaroga</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.6/39

Alkali / salt based formulations

Root and whole plant are used in alkali extraction and salt based formulations. They are indicated in conditions such as abdominal distension, abdominal lump, indigestion, piles, *Shlipada* (filariasis/elephantiasis), *Galaganda* (goiter), sprue syndrome, *Apachi* (scrofula/lymph node swelling) and anorexia. Studies on *Kantakari Kshara* indicate its potential anti-inflammatory and bronchodilatory effects.^[21]

Table No. 13: Kantakari used in Alkali extraction / salt based formulations form

No.	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Dashamula Lavana</i>	<i>Anaharuja</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.26/24
2.	<i>Kalyanaka Lavana</i>	<i>Gulma, Ajirna, Arsha, Kasa</i>	Root	Su.Chi.4/32
3.	<i>Paniya Kshara Yoga</i>	<i>Shlipada, Galaganda, Grahani</i>	Whole plant	Su.Chi.19/63

Enema

Root, whole plant and fruit are used in medicated enema formulations. They are indicated in conditions such as musculoskeletal disorders, abdominal distension, *Stambha* (stiffness), rejuvenative therapy, aphrodisiac therapy, pain, diarrhea, cough, asthma/dyspnea, abdominal lump, urinary calculi and other *Svara Roga* (voice disorders). They are also used in *Sadatura* (chronically ill person) and for rejuvenative and aphrodisiac purposes.

Table No. 14: Kantakari used in enema formulations.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Dashamuladi Uttarabasti</i>	<i>Rakta Gulma</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.5/167
2.	<i>Dashamulika Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.13/65
3.	<i>Dashamulika Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.13/65
4.	<i>Dashamulika Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.14/137
5.	<i>Dashamula Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Gudabhramsha</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.19/45
6.	<i>Shatpushpadi Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Pittatisara</i>	Fruit	Cha.Chi.19/62
7.	<i>Pippalyadi Pichchha Basti</i>	<i>Shula, Pravahika</i>	Fruit	Cha.Chi.19/118
8.	<i>Bilva Taila Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Kaphavrita Vata</i>	Fruit	Cha.Chi.19/119
9.	<i>Dashamula Kshira Basti</i>	<i>Udavarta, Mahayoni</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.30/111
10.	<i>Baladi Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	Cha.Si.3/14
11.	<i>Dashamula Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	Cha.Si.3/35
12.	<i>Dvipanchamuladi Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Kaphajaroga, Atopa, Mutrasanga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.3/59
13.	<i>Erandamuladi Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Vatajaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.3/38
14.	<i>Chandanadi Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Daha, Atisara</i>	Root	Cha.Si.3/58
15.	<i>Dashmuladi Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Pitajaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.3/59
16.	<i>Punarnavadi Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Samsargaja Roga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.3/66
17.	<i>Bilva Taila Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Vatajaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.3/ 70
18.	<i>Dashamuladhya Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Vatajaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.4/4
19.	<i>Dashamuladi Vasa Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	Cha.Si.4/7
20.	<i>Saindhavadi Taila Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Kaphaja Roga, Anaha, Ashmari</i>	Root	Cha.Si.4/15
21.	<i>Yavadi Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Angavyatha</i>	Root	Cha.Si.7/47
22.	<i>Shatahvadi Anuvasana</i>	<i>Vatajaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.4/8
23.	<i>Dashamula Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Klama Basti Vyapada</i>	Root	Cha.Si.7/20
24.	<i>Dashamulika Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Pakvashayasthita Basti</i>	Root	Cha.Si.7/38
25.	<i>Panchamula Basti</i>	<i>Urasthita Basti</i>	Root	Cha.Si.7/39
26.	<i>Astaprasrutika Basti</i>	<i>Vatavridhi</i>	Root	Cha.Si.8/5
27.	<i>Shalaparnadi Basti</i>	<i>Vatajaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.10/19

28.	<i>Kalingadi Basti</i>	<i>Pashu Basti</i>	Root	Cha.Si.11/23
29.	<i>Pilukariradi Basti</i>	<i>Khara, Ushtra</i>	Root	Cha.Si.11/26
30.	<i>Navaprasrutika Basti</i>	<i>Vatajaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.8/6
31.	<i>Bilvadi Sura Siddha Basti</i>	<i>Vataprakopa in Basti</i>	Root	Cha.Si.9/8
32.	<i>Bilvadi Basti</i>	<i>Vatajaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.10/19
33.	<i>Punarnavadi Niruha Basti</i>	<i>Sada Atura</i>	Root	Cha.Si.11/32
34.	<i>Baladi Anuvasana Basti</i>	<i>Sada Atura</i>	Root	Cha.Si.11/35
35.	<i>Mustadi Yapana</i>	<i>Kshata, Kshina</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/15/1
36.	<i>Erandamuladi Yapana Basti</i>	<i>Urahakshata, Arsha</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Si.12/15/2
37.	<i>Sahacharadi Yapana Basti</i>	<i>Urahakshata</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Si.12/15/4
38.	<i>Prathama Baladi Yapana Basti</i>	<i>Kasa, Savasa</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Si.12/15/5
39.	<i>Dvitiya Baladi Yapana Basti</i>	<i>Gulma, Kasa, Jvara</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/15/6
40.	<i>Laghupanchamuladi Yapana Basti</i>	<i>Vishama Jvara</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/15/8
41.	<i>Sthiradi Yapana Basti</i>	<i>Vajikarana</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/15/12
42.	<i>Tittaryadi Basti</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/16/1
43.	<i>Dvipanchamuladi Basti</i>	<i>Balya</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/16/2
44.	<i>Mayuradi Basti</i>	<i>Balya</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/16/2
45.	<i>Dashamuladi Basti</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/16/9
46.	<i>Dvipanchamuladi Basti</i>	<i>Sheleshma Vyadhi, Mutraroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/18
47.	<i>Dashamula Mayuradi Basti</i>	<i>Anilaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.12/18
48.	<i>Vachadi Taila Anuvasana</i>	<i>Vatarogi, Gulma, Anaha</i>	Root	Su.Chi.37/13
49.	<i>Bhulikadi Taila Anuvasana</i>	<i>Vata Vikara</i>	Root	Su.Chi.37/19
50.	<i>Guduchyadi Asthapana</i>	<i>Sarvamaruta Rogaghna, Vayasthapana</i>	Root	Su.Chi.38/47
51.	<i>Dashamuladi Asthapana</i>	<i>Kapharoga, Krimi, Mutra Maruta Sanga</i>	Root	Su.Chi.38/64
52.	<i>Baladi Asthapana</i>	<i>Jivaniya, Sarvagada</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.4/1
53.	<i>Dvipanchamuladi Niruha</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.4/4
54.	<i>Erandamuladi Niruha</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi, Hradaroga, Gulma, Vibandha, Kushtha</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.4/7
55.	<i>Siddha Basti</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.4/33
56.	<i>Gomutra Basti</i>	<i>Kaphaja Vyadhi</i>	Fruit, Root	A.H.Ka.4/34
57.	<i>Mrigadi Basti</i>	<i>Vrushya</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.4/43
58.	<i>Godhadi Basti</i>	<i>Vajikarana</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.4/49
59.	<i>Dashamuladi Anuvasana</i>	<i>Vatavikara</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.4/54
60.	<i>Panchamula Taila Anuvasana</i>	<i>Kaphahara</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.4/66
61.	<i>Dashamulika Niruha</i>	<i>Pakvashayasthita Basti</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.5/18
62.	<i>Panchamulika Niruha</i>	<i>Stambha, Adhmana</i>	Root	A.H.Ka.5/32

Medicated lentil soups

Whole plant, root and fruit are used in medicated lentil soups. Internally, they are administered in asthma/dyspnea, cough and hiccup,

Table No. 15: *Kantakari* used in medicated lentil soup form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Nidigdihikadi Yusha</i>	<i>Hikka, Svasa</i>	Fruit	Cha.Chi.17/95
2.	<i>Rasnadi Yusha</i>	<i>Svasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.17/96
3.	<i>Kantakari Siddha Mudaga Yusha</i>	<i>Vataja Kasa</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.18/184
4.	<i>Nidigdihikadi Mudaga Yusha</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut. 52/24
5.	<i>Kantakari Yusha</i>	<i>Sarva Kasa</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.3/176
6.	<i>Dashamula Yusha</i>	<i>Hikka, Svasa</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.4/20
7.	<i>Vyaghryadi Yusha</i>	<i>Hikka, Svasa</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.4/20

Medicated gruel

Root and whole plant are used in medicated gruel preparations. They are administered in conditions such as cough, asthma, hiccup, urinary disorders, cardiac disorders, and abdominal diseases.

Table No. 16: *Kantakari* used in medicated gruel form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Dashamulishrita Yavagu</i>	<i>Kasa, Hikka, Svasa</i>	Root	Cha.Su.2/27
2.	<i>Panchamula Sadhita Yavagu</i>	<i>Udara</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.13/99
3.	<i>Dashamuladi Yavagu</i>	<i>Kasa, Hikka, Svasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.17/102
4.	<i>Panchamula Siddha Yavagu</i>	<i>Hridaroga</i>	Root	Cha.Si.9/ 8
5.	<i>Vyaghrigokshura Yavagu</i>	<i>Mutraghata</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.11/38

Thin gruel

Root and whole plant are used in thin gruel preparations. They are administered in conditions such as cough, asthma, hiccup, diarrhea, abdominal lump, urinary disorders, cardiac disorders, fever, tuberculosis, pain in the chest-flank-head region and *Visha Roga* (toxic disorders).

Table No. 17: *Kantakari* used in thin gruel form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Laghupanchamula Peya</i>	<i>Vataja Atisara</i>	Root	Cha.Su.2/19
2.	<i>Kantakari Gokshura Peya</i>	<i>Mutrakrichchha</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Su.2/22
3.	<i>Svadamstra Kantakari Peya</i>	<i>Parshva Basti Shiroruja</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.3/181
4.	<i>Panchamuli Shrita Peya</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.5/167
5.	<i>Panchamulika Peya</i>	<i>Rajayakshma</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.8/69
6.	<i>Dashamula Peya</i>	<i>Vataja Kasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.18/79
7.	<i>Panchamula Peya</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	Root	Su.Ut.42/55

8.	<i>Dashamuladi Peya</i>	<i>Vataja Kasa</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.3/22
9.	<i>Dashamuladi Peya</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa, Hikka</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.4/23

Medicated meat soup

Root and whole plant are used in medicated meat soup preparations. They are administered in conditions such as cough, asthma and *Vataroga* (nervous system disorders).

Table No. 18: *Kantakari* used in medicated meat soup form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Dashamulasiddha Mamsarasa</i>	<i>Svasa, Kasa</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.17/94
2.	<i>Ajashirshadi Mamsarasa</i>	<i>Vataroga</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.28/107
3.	<i>Kasamardadi Mamsarasa</i>	<i>Kaphaja Kasa</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Chi.3/42

Medicated water

Root and whole plant are used in medicated water. They are used for conditions such as cough, *Madatyaya* (alcoholism), *Svarabheda* (hoarseness of voice), *Pratishyaya* (rhinitis), abdominal lump, *Ama* (indigestion), *Kamala* (jaundice), neuromuscular disorders, *Svayathu* (edema) and for *Anulomana* (regulation of movement of *Vata*).

Table No. 19: *Kantakari* used in medicated water form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Kantakarishrita Jala</i>	<i>Vata Varcha Anulomana</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.13/128
2.	<i>Sthiradishrita Jala</i>	<i>Kamala</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.16/114
3.	<i>Panchamulika Jala</i>	<i>Vatika Madatyaya</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.24/129
4.	<i>Kantakarishrita Jala</i>	<i>Madatyaya</i>	Whole plant	Cha.Chi.24/164
5.	<i>Laghupanchamulashrita Jala</i>	<i>Vataja Svarabheda</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.26/284
6.	<i>Dashamula Ambu</i>	<i>Kaphaja Kasa</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.3/44
7.	<i>Panchamulashrita Vari</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	Root	A.H.Chi.14/112
8.	<i>Dashamula Ambu</i>	<i>Pinasa</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.20/4

External paste application

Root and whole plant are used in external medicated paste formulations. They are applied in conditions such as *Svitra* (leucoderma), *Charmadala* (skin diseases), inflammation, *Indralupta* (alopecia), *Svagraha* (paediatric disorders), poisoning and for *Stanya Shodhana* (purification of breast milk). Root paste is applied in *Vishadrishta* (snake bite/poisonous bite).

Table No. 20: *Kantakari* used in external paste application form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Dashamula Lepa</i>	<i>Vatahara</i>	Root	Cha.Su.3/19
2.	<i>Panchamula Lepa</i>	<i>Stanya Shodhana</i>	Root	Cha.Chi.30/270
3.	<i>Tilvakadi Lepa</i>	<i>Svitra</i>	Whole plant	Su.Chi.9/28
4.	<i>Simhimuladi Mukhalepa</i>	<i>Shishirarutu Lepa</i>	Root	A.H.Su.22/19
5.	<i>Kshudravartaka Svarasa Lepa</i>	<i>Indulupta</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Ut.24/30
6.	<i>Vyaghrimula Lepa</i>	<i>Vishadrashta</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.35/47
7.	<i>Palindyadi Lepa</i>	<i>Mushika Visha</i>	Root	A.H.Ut.38/20

Collyrium

Whole plant and flower are used in collyrium stick. They are used in *Netraroga* (eye diseases).

Table No. 21: *Kantakari* used in colyrium form.

No	Formulation	Indication	Part used	Reference
1.	<i>Putikaranjadi Varti Anjana</i>	<i>Kaphaja Abhisyaanda</i>	Whole plant	Su.Ut.11/9
2.	<i>Patlyadi Varti Anjana</i>	<i>Rakta Abhishyaanda</i>	flower	Su.Ut.12/11
3.	<i>Pundradi Varti Anjana</i>	<i>Netraroga</i>	Whole plant	A.H.Ut.11/49

Roasted flour preparation

Whole plant is used in *Vyoshadi Saktu* and is used in all *Santarpanotha Vyadhi* (diseases caused by overindulgence).^[22]

Different food preparation

Root is used in *Panchamula Kvatha Siddha* various food preparations and it is taken in abdominal diseases and weak digestion power.^[23]

Medicated smocking stick

Whole plant is used in *Kasaghna Dhumavarti* for cough.^[24] In ethnomedicine, fumigation with the whole plant is used in piles,^[25] while fumigation with the seeds mixed in mustard oil is employed in dental caries, toothache, swelling and pus.^[26]

Errhine insufflation

Whole plant is used in *Madanadi Pradhamana Nasya* for *Udavarta* (upward movement of *Vata*).^[27] Nasal administration of the powder of the whole plant is useful in reducing migraine and headache.^[28]

DISCUSSION

Kantakari (*Solanum virginianum* L.), a member of the Solanaceae family, is a non-toxic and

safe medicinal plant widely valued in both Ayurvedic and modern pharmacological research for its diverse therapeutic properties. This review aims to systematically evaluate the use of *Kantakari* as an ingredient in various Ayurvedic formulations. A total of 320 formulations containing *Kantakari* were identified, of which 225 formulations are intended for internal administration, while 95 formulations are used externally. Among them *Ghrita* noted as highest number of preparations intended for internal administration, whereas *Basti* accounted for the greatest number of formulations used externally. Distribution of *Kantakari*-based formulations across various Ayurvedic compendiums shows that Charaka Samhita documented the highest number, with 148 formulations as mentioned in Graph no: 1.

0	Charaka Samhita	Susruta Samhita	Ashtanga Hridaya	Total
Internal	93	45	87	225
External	55	12	28	95
Total	148	57	115	320

Graph No. 1.1: Number of formulations for internal and external use mentioned in Brihadatrayi

Kantakari is used as an ingredient in various dosage forms, including *Svarasa*, *Kalka*, *Kvatha*, *Churna*, *Gutika/ Vataka*, *Kshirapaka*, *Avaleha*, *Sandhana* (*Asava* and *Arishta*), *Taila*, *Ghrita*, other *Sneha* (*Vasa*, *Majja*, or *Mahasneha*), *Kshara/ Lavana*, *Basti* (*Niruha/Anuvasana*), *Anjana*, *Dhumavarti*, and *Pradhamana Nasya*. It is also incorporated in *Pathya Kalpana* such as *Yusha*, *Yavagu*, *Peya*, *Mamsarasa*, *Siddha Jala*, *Panaka*, *Saktu*, *Shashkuli*, and *Bhojya*, as depicted in Graph 1.2.

Graph no: 2 Different dosage forms of *Kantakari* available in different Ayurvedic texts

In this review, different plant parts such as Whole plant, Root, Fruit, Seed, *Pushpa*, *Patra*, and *Ankura* were found to be used in various preparations. Among these, Root was used in the highest number of preparations (216), followed by whole plant (99), fruit (9), Seed (2), leaves (1), flower (1), and flower bud (1), as depicted in Graph 1.3.

Graph no: 3 Part used of *Kantakari* in different preparations.

Various studies have also been conducted on its therapeutic significance in modern science.

The therapeutic effects of its different parts are presented in table 22.^[29]

Table no. 22: Therapeutic uses and actions of different parts of *Kantakari*.

Sr. No.	Part used	Therapeutic indications	Therapeutic actions
1.	Flower	Common cold, cough, exanthema, eye diseases, flatulence, pain	-
2.	Fruits	Asthma, bronchitis, common cold, cough, exanthema, flatulence, hepatomghaly, pain, pharyngitis, respiratory tract infections, skin diseases, splenic diseases, urinary blader calculi, urination disorders, vomiting	Expectorant, diuretic, fertility agent, laxative, general tonic for rejuvenation, anthelmintic, antirheumatic, antipyretic
3.	Leaf	Asthma, bronchitis, cough, fever, hemorrhoids, hepatomghaly, pain, respiratory tract infections, skin diseases, splenic diseases, urinary blader calculi, urination disorders, vomiting	Anthelmintic, antipyretic, antirheumatic, aphrodisiac, Expectorant, diuretic, fertility agent, laxative, general tonic for rejuvenation
4.	Root	Asthma, bronchitis, chest pain, chickenpox, common cold, cough, fever, heart diseases, hemorrhoids, pain, low back pain, thirst, urinary tract infections, vomiting,	Anthelmintic, aphrodisiac, appetite stimulant, laxative, expectorant
5.	Stem	Exanthema, eye diseases, flatulence, pain	-
6.	Whole plant	Fever	-

The details of the activity as per Ayurveda and the reported scientific studies confirming its long-term use are given in table no. 23.

Table No. 23: Classical *Karma* and corresponding scientific reported activity of *Kantakari*.

Sr. no.	Classical <i>Karma</i>	Reported activity
1.	<i>Kasaghna</i>	Antitussive ^[30]
2.	<i>Svasahara</i>	Antiasthmatic, ^[31] bronchodialating, ^[32] mast cell stabilizing ^[33]
3.	<i>Jvaraghna</i>	Antipyretic, ^[34] antibacterial, ^[35] antimicrobial ^[36]
4.	<i>Krimihara</i>	Anthelmintic, ³⁷ antibacterial ³⁸
5.	<i>Hrida</i> <i>Amayahara</i>	Cardiac stimulating, cardio-protective, ^[39] cardio vascular, ^[40] antiatherosclerotic, ^[41] hypo cholesterolaemic ^[42]
6.	<i>Pinasahara</i>	Mast cell stabilizing, ^[43] immunomodulatory, ^[44] antibacterial ^[45]
7.	<i>Kanduhara</i>	Mast cell stabilizing, ^[46] immunomodulatory, ^[47] antifungal ^[48]
8.	<i>Shothahara</i>	Anti-inflammatory ^[49]
9.	<i>Parshvapidahara</i>	Analgesic ^[50]
10.	<i>Mutrarogahara</i>	Diuretic ^[51]

CONCLUSION

This comprehensive review of formulations containing *Kantakari* highlights its extensive therapeutic relevance in Ayurvedic medicine as well as modern pharmacology. The analysis shows that medicated *Ghee* (74 formulations), enema (62 formulations) and decoction (36) represent the highest number of preparations. In total, *Kantakari* is documented in 320 formulations, of which 225 are intended for internal administration and 95 for external use. Among these, dyspnoea and cough are the most commonly reported indications. The plant demonstrates over 17 notable pharmacological activities and is indicated for the management of various clinical conditions. The predominant use of root in pharmaceutical preparations suggests its richness in diverse phytoconstituents, contributing to its therapeutic efficacy. Furthermore, well-designed clinical trials are crucial to identify optimal dosage forms and establish their effectiveness for specific disease conditions.

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